

Influence of Gender on Teachers' Contribution to Covid-19 Anxiety Level and Compliance to Preventive Protocols Among Secondary School Teachers in Delta South Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship of Covid-19 Anxiety and Compliance with preventive protocols among teachers in Delta South Senatorial District given to the fact that people resisted covid-19 compliance guidelines of the Delta State government to curtail the dreaded virus. Seven research questions guided the study and seven corresponding hypothesis were tested. The correlational research design was employed in the study. The population for the study comprised all secondary school teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. The population size was 1,989. A Sample of 320 teachers was drawn to make up the respondents using the multi-stage technique, which combined cluster, stratified, and random sampling techniques. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire. The psychometric properties of the instruments were determined and found adequate for use. Factor analysis and Principle Components analysis were used to test for the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficients and it yielded a coefficient of 0.837 and 0.717 for Covid-19 Anxiety Rating Scale and Compliance to Protocols Rating Scale respectively. Data collected were analysed using Pearson's Moment Correlation to answer the research questions and regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the analysis showed among others that; there was low level of compliance of teachers with low and moderate covi-19 preventive protocols. The study recommended that effect at enforcing compliance should be to intensify campaigns on the disastrous effects of Covid-19 and if possible, to expose teachers either through videos or life experience to infected persons with the ultimate aim of increasing the anxiety and fear of contacting the disease.

Keywords: Covid-19 anxiety level, secondary school, gender of teachers, compliance, influence, preventive protocols, Delta South Senatorial District

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INTRODUCTION

In the year 2019, there was an outbreak of covid-19 disease which eventually became a pandemic. The disease was airborne and was found to be prevalent in situations where human beings live in group, such as classrooms in schools, banking halls. There was a high level of anxiety among persons and this led to closure of activities and business operation, where people operate in crowd. Thus, business organizations like banking, activities in airport and educational institutions were closed down.

The World Health organization, in order to stem or reduce the spread of these disease put in place some protocols. For example, in the schools wash hand basins were provided such that teachers and pupils were required to wash their hands regularly with soap and running water. In addition, to the above, individuals were asked to reduce handshake and cover their mouth when they sneeze among others. It was observed that they were problems of compliance of individuals to these protocols.

Literature reveals that in disease condition, there is problem of compliance with preventive protocols, and literature equally shows that the extent to which individuals comply with protocols in disease condition depends on their anxiety level, considering the disease. According to Jeff Greenberg, Sheldon Solomon and Tom Pyszczynski in 1986 in their Terror Management Theory (TMT), 'Human beings are unique in their symbolic thoughts which foster their self-awareness and ability to reflect on the past and ponder the future. In other words, humans vary in their disposition to human trait such as anxiety about life especially in disease condition. This variation also influences their disposition to actions likely to avert the condition and death.

Despite the huge success of these measures across many countries, implementing them, and ensuring that people maintain social distance and refrain from unnecessary outdoor activities in authoritarian and liberal societies for weeks result into ultimate human challenge (Rooij et al., 2020). As schools are reopened after seven months forced lockdown, teachers are faced with both physical and psychological threats created by the COVID-19 pandemic. According to Grubic et al. (2020), efforts to control the spread through non-pharmaceutical interventions and preventive measures such as social-distancing and other protocols

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prompted both psychological and emotional effects on teachers, especially, teachers in secondary schools.

Zumla et al (2010), confirmed that the psychological impact of pandemic such as COVID-19 on teachers include anxiety, stress and depression among others. Kroenke et al (2017) opined that teachers' anxiety negatively affects students' academic performance; anxiety impairs focus and concentration, memory and visual motor skills which may lead to stress.

No study to the knowledge of these authors has investigated the Covid-19 anxiety level of teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. Secondly, no study has investigated how the anxiety level of teachers will be related to compliance to protocols aimed at checking the spread of the disease in the above population.

Statement of the Problem

The problem of this study is; how does secondary school teachers gender influence their covid-19 anxiety level? Secondly, what is the influence of teachers gender and their level of anxiety on compliance to covid-19 preventive protocols?

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the present study is; to ascertain the covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers in secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District.

Secondly, it intense to ascertain if teachers gender and their level of covid-19 anxiety has influence on their adherence to covid-19 protocols.

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Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the mean covid-19 anxiety level by teachers gender in Delta South Senatorial District?
2. What is the mean compliance to preventive protocols level by teacher gender in Delta South Senatorial District?

Hypotheses:

The study tested the following hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean compliance to covid-19 preventive protocols of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Methodology:

The Correlational Survey Design was used in conducting the study. The population of the study consisted of 1,989 Secondary School Teachers in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta state comprising of the 8 local governments. The sample size for this study is 320; this is judged to be adequate at 0.05 alpha level of significance according to Krejcie R.V. and Morgan D.W. (1970) in their table for 'Determining sample size. The sampling Technique employed was Multi stage Techniques in which we stratified teachers into male and female using Stratified Random Sampling techniques. In order to ensure that all the

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teachers get equal representation, the researcher will select 16.08% of the total population of the teachers in each secondary school. The research instrument that was used in the study is questionnaire, which was self-constructed with a title “Covid-19 Anxiety and Compliance Assessment to Protocols (CACAP)”. The questionnaire items were designed to measure and elicit response on the level of anxiety and compliance of secondary school teachers to Covid-19 preventive protocols in Delta South Senatorial District of Delta State.

This questionnaire is divided into two sections, A, and B. Section A contains respondents personal data (demographic data) like; Name (optional), Sex/Gender, name of school, age, marital status and location of school. While section B consists of two sub-scales, which was in line with W.H.O recommended COVID-19 prevention protocols; this will measure Covid-19 anxiety and compliance to protocols scale with 32 items on a Four-Point scale, ranging from Strongly Disagreed (SD) =1, Disagreed (D) =2, Agreed (A) =3, and Strongly Agreed (SA) =4.

The instrument for this study had face and content validity. The content validity was ensured in the study by generating items in the questionnaire through item-response to measure all the necessary areas which the study sought to analyse. This was carried out by generating items that will answer each research questions. Items in the question for this study were self-constructed after careful review of concepts of anxiety and compliance. Factor analysis was used to ensure the content and construct validity of the instrument. The principle component analysis of the extraction method was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument. The reliability of the item was ascertained using a pre-trial test of the instrument which was carried out on 60 teachers in Delta South Senatorial District. The

result of the test was used to compute the reliability of the instrument. The Cronbach Alpha was applied for the computation of the reliability coefficient, and a coefficient value of 0.837 was obtained for Covid-19 Anxiety level Scale, whereas, 0.717 was obtained for Compliance to Protocols Scale. The researcher was personally involved in the distribution of the questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the teachers in the various secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District.

The investigation requested the teachers to respond fairly and honestly, since their responses would be treated with utmost confidentiality, of which the researcher established a rapport with the respondents for easy administration of the questionnaire. They were given forty minutes (40 minutes) to answer the questionnaire; the researcher waited and retrieved the completed copies from them. T-test was used to answer the research questions, and also the independent t-test statistics was used to test for the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels.

Results:

Table 1: t-test comparison of the mean covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t.cal.	Sign. level
Male	131	2.54	0.84	1.03	0.05
Female	189	2.44	0.90		

Table 1 show that the numbers of male and female are 131 and 189, while mean covid-19 anxiety level scores for male and female teachers are 2.54 and 2.44, with standard deviation

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scores of 0.84 and 0.90 respectively. In other words, the difference in the mean covid-19 anxiety level is 0.103 at 0.05 level of significant.

Table 2: t-test comparison of the mean Compliance to covid-19 protocols by male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Gender	N	Mean	S.D	t.cal.	Sign. level
Male	131	2.53	0.75	0.24	0.05
Female	189	2.51	0.77		

Table 2 show that the numbers of male and female are 131 and 189, while mean compliance to covid-19 protocols scores for male and female teachers are 2.53 and 2.51, with standard deviation scores of 0.75 and 0.77 respectively. In other words, the difference in the mean compliance to covid-19 anxiety level is 0.021 at 0.05 level of significant.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in mean covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Table 3: t-test comparison of the mean covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers

Gender	N	Mean	Std.	Df.	t.cal	t.cri.	Sign	Decision
Male	131	2.54	0.84	318	1.03	1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female	189	2.44	0.90					

Table 3 is the result test for hypotheses one. The t-calculated value of 1.03 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 at a significant level of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning there is no significant difference in the mean covid-19 anxiety level of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in mean compliance to covid-19 anxiety protocols of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Table 4: t-test comparison of the mean compliance to covid-19 anxiety protocols of male and female teachers

Gender	N	Mean	Std.	Df.	t.cal	t.cri.	Signf.	Decision
Male	131	2.53	0.75	318	0.24	1.96	0.05	Accepted
Female	189	2.51	0.77					

Table 4 is the result test for hypotheses two. The t-calculated value of 0.24 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96 at a significant level of 0.05. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted, meaning there is no significant difference in the mean compliance to covid-19 anxiety preventive protocols of male and female teachers in Delta South Senatorial District.

Discussions:

The finding indicates that there is no significant difference in gender in covid-19 anxiety and compliance with preventive protocols. This finding is contrary to the research of Galasso et al, 2020; where they opined that gender differences are strong both in beliefs and behaviour. In a survey carried out by Bargain et al, (2020), in eight OECD countries (Australia, Austria, France, Germany, Italy, New Zealand, UK & USA) where they interviewed a total of 21,649 respondents in two waves. They observed that women are more likely to take the pandemic seriously.

Foucault et al, (2020) opined that gender differences in beliefs and behaviours remained sizeable when we control for individual socio-demographic characteristics and psychological

factors such as risk aversion, trust towards scientists, and the perceived likelihood to be infected as well as political ideology. The differences are only partially mitigated for individuals cohabiting with direct exposure to covid-19.

The observed differences between the way men and women have adjusted to the new risks associated with COVID-19 is echoed in behavioural differences between male and female leaders. Countries led by women have generally responded more effectively to the pandemic than countries led by men (Garikipati & Kambhampti, 2020).

Conclusions

Based on the findings summarized above, the following conclusions are made in the study:

That; gender of teachers' in Covid-19 anxiety does not influence the level of Covid-19 compliance with preventive protocols.

Recommendation:

In view of these findings, the following recommendations were made;

1. Effect at enforcing the compliance of preventive protocols, is to intensify campaign on the disastrous effect of Covid-19 pandemic.

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